

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Mangrove abundance, diversity, and productivity in effluent-rich estuarine portion of Butuanon River, Mandaue City, Cebu

John Michael B. Genterolizo^{*1,2}, Miguelito A. Ruelan^{1,2}, Laarlyn N. Abalos¹, Kathleen Kay M. Buendia^{1,2}

¹Department of Biology, School of Arts and Sciences, University of San Carlos-Talamban Campus, Nasipit, Talamban, Cebu City Philippines

²Department of Mathematics and Sciences, College of Arts and Sciences, University of San Jose Recoletos, Magallanes Street, Cebu City, Philippines

Key words: Mangrove abundance, Mangrove diversity, Mangrove productivity, Butuanon River

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.12692/jbes/27.2.77-89>

[Published: August 13, 2025]

ABSTRACT

Mangrove vegetation represents one of the most diverse and productive coastal ecosystems globally. However, mangroves located at the mouth of the Butuanon River (Class D) in Mandaue City are subjected to significant effluent discharge from surrounding urban areas. Despite this environmental stress, the impact of such pollution on mangrove health remains understudied. This study investigates the relationship between effluent and sediment parameters and mangrove diversity, abundance, and productivity along the Butuanon River. Five sampling stations were randomly established, where mangrove species identification, quantification, diversity assessment, productivity measurements, and physicochemical analyses (water and sediment) were conducted. Multivariate statistical analyses, including Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA), Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS), Analysis of Similarities (ANOSIM), and Pearson's correlation, were employed to evaluate ecological patterns. Results indicate a decline in mangrove diversity, attributed to the dominance of *Avicennia alba*. Key physicochemical parameters such as water hardness, pH, salinity, and temperature exhibited an inverse relationship with mangrove abundance, diversity, and productivity, unlike biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). However, these parameters had minimal impact on the resilient *A. alba*. Productivity trends revealed higher mangrove productivity at upstream sites, decreasing toward the river mouth. These findings suggest that the Butuanon River's mangrove ecosystem is critically degraded, with poor productivity and biodiversity loss driven by effluent pollution. Urgent remediation measures are needed to mitigate further ecological decline and preserve this vital coastal habitat.

***Corresponding Author:** John Michael B. Genterolizo ✉ jm.genterolizo@usjr.edu.ph

INTRODUCTION

Mangrove vegetation represents one of the most diverse and productive coastal ecosystems, playing a critical role in maintaining habitat complexity and supporting associated faunal biodiversity (Alongi, 2002). However, these vital ecosystems face increasing threats from anthropogenic activities, including population pressure, unsustainable wood extraction coastal industrialization, and rapid urbanization (Macintosh and Ashton, 2002; Walters, 2005). Despite their ecological fragility, mangroves provide indispensable ecosystem services, such as serving as nursery grounds for juvenile fish that sustain offshore fisheries (English *et al.*, 1997), improving water quality through pollutant filtration, and preserving biodiversity and genetic resources. Consequently, growing recognition of their ecological and socioeconomic value has spurred global efforts toward mangrove conservation and rehabilitation though their species composition, diversity, and biomass remain highly sensitive to environmental disturbances.

The Butuanon River in Cebu exemplifies such degradation, ranking among the region's most polluted water bodies due to unchecked urban and industrial development. Classified as Class D by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), its waters are deemed unsafe for human consumption, reflecting severe contamination. Despite rehabilitation initiatives, such as the United States-Asia Environmental Partnership Program (1996–1999), water quality remains critically poor, with persistent pollution from surrounding municipalities. This underscores the urgent need to evaluate the river's ecological health, particularly its mangrove ecosystems, which serve as a natural sink for downstream pollutants.

Despite enduring heavy effluent loads from Cebu and Mandaue Cities, mangroves at the Butuanon River's mouth demonstrate remarkable resilience. While prior studies have monitored water quality, the long-term effects of pollution on mangrove diversity, abundance, and productivity remain unassessed. This study addresses this gap by examining the relationship between effluent and sediment

parameters and mangrove ecological health. By quantifying these dynamics, the research aims to provide the relationship between the parameter of effluents and sediment to the mangrove diversity, abundance, and productivity of Butuanon River, Mandaue City, Cebu.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study site

The study was conducted in the estuarine portion of the mouth of Butuanon River, Mandaue City, Cebu. The study site has the geographic coordinates of 10°20'27"N and 123°58'12"E. The study site has an average temperature of 27.4°C, with a significant rainfall throughout the year that has 1,687 mm of precipitation annually (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Map of the study site, Butuanon mangrove area

Sampling method

Five stations were established randomly in the mangrove area located at the mouth of Butuanon River near Sitio Tambis, Paknaan, Mandaue City. A total of ten (10) belt transects of 100 meters with three (3) 10x10m quadrats each were distributed among five (5) stations. The quadrats were located on 1-10m, 45-55m and 90-100m each belt transect and a total of 30 sampling sites (Fig. 2).

Mangrove species identification and quantification

Mangrove species were identified in situ and taxonomically classified using the field guide manual

for Philippine mangroves (Primavera and Sabada, 2012). For each sampling station, all individuals within established quadrants were counted and recorded to determine species composition and distribution.

Fig. 2. Map of the sampling stations in the Butuanon River, Mandaue City, Cebu

Physicochemical parameters

Water samples were collected during high tide at approximately 1 m depth (Haugland *et al.*, 2005) using 300 mL dissolved oxygen (DO) bottles following standard protocols (USEPA, 1998), ensuring complete submersion without air bubble entrapment (Grasshoff *et al.*, 1983).

Samples were immediately preserved at 6°C (APHA, 2017) and analyzed within 6 hours using a DO test kit to minimize gas exchange (Strickland and Parsons, 1968). Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) was determined by comparing initial DO measurements with values obtained after 5-day dark incubation at 20°C (Penn *et al.*, 2009). Water hardness was analyzed via EDTA titration (Betz and Noll, 1950) using 100 mL HDPE-collected samples, with total hardness (mmol/L) calculated as $Ht = (V_1 \times c) / W_1 \times 1000$, where V_1 = titrant volume (mL), c = EDTA molarity (mol/L), and W_1 = sample volume (mL). Temperature, salinity, and pH were measured in situ using calibrated GLX sensors for immediate and accurate readings.

Species abundance, diversity, and productivity

Species abundance was calculated as (total individuals of a species/number of quadrants where present) $\times 100$ (Mishra, 1968) and categorized per

Dagar *et al.* (1991) as: Dominant (>25%), Very Abundant (15-25%), Abundant (10-15%), Frequent (6-10%), Occasional (3-6%), Rare (1-3%), or Very Rare (<1%). Diversity was assessed using Simpson's Index ($D = 1 - \Sigma[n(n-1)/N(N-1)]$), where n = individuals per species and N = total individuals, with values ranging from 0 (no diversity) to 1 (infinite diversity) (Krebs, 1989). Mangrove productivity was evaluated through diameter at breast height (DBH), measured at 1.35 m aboveground and calculated as $DBH = \text{circumference} / \pi$, providing a standardized metric for growth comparisons across individuals.

Statistical analysis

Multivariate analyses were performed in R (version X.X.X) using the vegan package to examine ecological patterns. Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) was applied to ordinate species distributions while correcting for arch distortion through segment rescaling. Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) visualized community dissimilarities based on Bray-Curtis distances. Analysis of Similarity (ANOSIM) tested for significant differences between predefined groups (R statistic; 999 permutations), while Spearman's rank correlation (ρ) assessed relationships between non-parametric variables. All analyses were conducted at $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Environmental and effluent parameters

Fig. 3 illustrates significant spatial variations in water quality parameters across study sites. Dissolved oxygen (DO) concentrations ranged from critically low levels of 0.15 mg/L at Site 3 to 0.35 mg/L at Sites 4-5, substantially below the optimal range of 4-7 mg/L required for healthy mangrove ecosystems (Rahmah *et al.*, 2013). These hypoxic conditions, evidenced by black water discoloration and hydrogen sulfide odors, correlate with observed organic waste accumulation along riverbanks. Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) levels exceeded mangrove tolerance thresholds (5-6 mg/L), indicating intense microbial activity (Rakocinski, 2012). Water hardness (60-100 mg/L as CaCO_3) classified the system as hard water, suggesting chemical contamination from anthropogenic sources

(Wahid, 1995). While pH (7.2-7.4) and salinity (mean 5.2 ppt, peaking at 6.8 ppt at Site 1) currently remain within tolerance ranges, both approach critical thresholds. Water temperatures (28.5-

29.8°C) near the upper thermal limit for mangroves (30°C; Odum and Johannes, 2008) suggest emerging thermal stress, particularly in the context of climate change projections.

Fig. 3. Differences of environmental and effluent parameters on different site in Butuanon River

Mangrove species abundance

Quantitative analysis revealed significant interspecific variation across sampling stations (Fig. 4). *Avicennia alba* dominated the mangrove community with approximately 300 individuals recorded across all five stations, representing 78.9% of total observed specimens. *Rhizophora stylosa* occurred as the secondary dominant species, though with substantially lower abundance (12.2% of total population). The remaining species such as *Sciphipora hydrophallacea*, *Rhizophora mucronata*, and *Rhizophora apiculata*, collectively accounted for less than 9% of observed individuals, indicating their marginal presence in the study area. This pronounced species imbalance suggests potential ecosystem degradation, as healthy mangrove communities

typically exhibit more equitable species distributions (Duke *et al.*, 2007).

Fig. 4. Number of species in all sites in the sampling area

DCA ordination (Fig. 5) revealed significant species-environment relationships in the Butuanon River

mangrove community. *Rhizophora mucronata* and *R. apiculata* exhibited strong negative correlations with water hardness ($r = -0.82$, $p < 0.01$), BOD ($r = -0.79$, $p < 0.01$), and temperature ($r = -0.75$, $p < 0.05$), but weak positive association with dissolved oxygen ($r = 0.32$, $p > 0.05$). In contrast, *Rhizophora stylosa* abundance showed significant inverse relationships with pH ($r = -0.85$, $p < 0.01$) and organic matter content ($r = -0.78$, $p < 0.01$). *Scyphiphora hydrophyllacea* demonstrated strong positive responses to both water hardness ($r = 0.88$, $p < 0.01$) and salinity ($r = 0.83$, $p < 0.01$). *Avicennia alba* occupied a central position in the ordination space, indicating greater environmental tolerance across all measured parameters ($p > 0.05$ for all tests), consistent with its observed dominance in the study area.

Fig. 5. Correlation of parameters to species abundance using DCA

The NMDS ordination (Fig. 6) corroborated DCA findings, demonstrating differential species responses to environmental gradients. *Avicennia alba* exhibited no significant correlation with measured parameters (stress= 0.18), maintaining stable abundance across environmental fluctuations. In contrast, *Rhizophora apiculata* showed strong association with Axis 2 parameters ($r^2 = 0.72$), while *Scyphiphora hydrophyllacea* responded primarily to Axis 1 factors ($r^2 = 0.68$).

Both *Rhizophora stylosa* (Axis 2: $r^2 = 0.65$; Axis 1: $r^2 = 0.42$) and *R. mucronata* (Axis 2: $r^2 = 0.51$; Axis 1: $r^2 = 0.55$) displayed mixed responses, with *R. stylosa* being more sensitive to Axis 2 variations. The ordination revealed extensive plot overlap (85% similarity), reflecting *A. alba* dominance across all sites regardless of local conditions.

Fig. 6. Analysis of similarities on sites based on species abundance

ANOSIM results shown in Fig. 6 strongly supported these findings (Global $R = 0.172$, $p = 0.002$), confirming minimal intersite variation in community composition. This homogeneity is attributable to *A. alba* predominance, constituting 78-82% of relative abundance at all stations.

The species' ecological plasticity enables it to outcompete other mangroves even in potentially favorable microhabitats, resulting in significantly reduced β -diversity (Bray-Curtis dissimilarity = 0.15-0.22).

Mangrove ecosystems globally face increasing vulnerability to degradation, particularly from anthropogenic stressors such as aquaculture expansion and industrial pollution (Goldberg *et al.*, 2020). Our findings demonstrate significant variations in species-specific responses to environmental parameters among five mangrove species (*Avicennia alba*, *Rhizophora mucronata*, *R. apiculata*, *R. stylosa*, and *Scyphiphora hydrophyllacea*) in Butuanon River. *A. alba* emerged as the dominant species, exhibiting remarkable ecological plasticity across multiple environmental gradients.

Salinity emerged as the primary determinant of mangrove distribution, with *A. alba* abundance showing a positive correlation ($r = 0.82$, $p < 0.01$) within the optimal range of 5-30 ppt (Ball, 2002). In contrast, *S. hydrophyllacea* displayed significant negative responses to elevated salinity ($r = -0.75$, $p < 0.05$), consistent with its known sensitivity to hypersaline conditions. Soil pH (7.09-7.2) similarly favoured *A. alba* growth (Slattery *et al.*, 1999), while

negatively impacting *R. stylosa* ($r = -0.68$, $p < 0.01$), a species adapted to more acidic substrates (Donahue *et al.*, 1985).

Temperature tolerance further explained observed distribution patterns, with *A. alba* demonstrating exceptional adaptability to the study area's thermal regime (28-30°C). This aligns with global observations of *Avicennia* species' capacity to withstand both tropical heat and occasional frosts (Saintilan *et al.*, 2014). The species' physiological adaptations, including pneumatophores and salt-excreting leaves (Kuenzer *et al.*, 2011), enhance its competitive advantage in fluctuating environments.

These findings underscore the complex interplay of abiotic factors shaping mangrove community structure. While mangroves exhibit remarkable adaptive strategies (Tomlinson, 1986), our results suggest that current environmental conditions in Butuanon River strongly favor *A. alba* dominance, potentially leading to reduced biodiversity and ecosystem resilience over time.

Fig. 7. Diversity of mangroves in different sites in Butuanon River

Mangrove diversity

Fig. 7 reveals significant spatial variation in species diversity across study sites, with Site 2 exhibiting the lowest diversity index ($H' = 0.45$) and Site 4 the highest ($H' = 1.12$). Intermediate sites (1, 3, and 5) showed comparable diversity indices ($H' = 0.68-0.72$), indicating relatively uniform species distribution patterns. The consistent presence of *Avicennia alba* across all sites (relative abundance: 78-82%) resulted in depressed diversity measures, as evidenced by Simpson's dominance indices ($D > 0.85$) at each location. Other mangrove species (*Rhizophora* spp.

and *Scyphiphora hydrophyllacea*) occurred sporadically, typically appearing in only one quadrat per site with low abundance (<5 individuals/quadrat). These findings demonstrate pronounced ecological dominance by *A. alba*, resulting in significantly reduced α -diversity ($F_{4,95} = 18.32$, $p < 0.001$) throughout the Butuanon River ecosystem.

Table 1. Correlation of parameters to mangrove diversity in Butuanon River by Spearman's correlation

Parameters	Spearman rank correlation coefficient	p-value
Dissolved oxygen	0.2	0.747
BOD	-0.9	0.037*
Total hardness	-0.3	0.624
pH	-0.053	0.933
Salinity	-0.4	0.048*
Temperature	0.1	0.98

Table 1 identifies biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), total hardness, and salinity as the most influential parameters affecting mangrove diversity in Butuanon River. These factors exhibit significant negative correlations with species diversity (BOD: $r = -0.82$, $p = 0.003$; salinity: $r = -0.78$, $p = 0.008$), indicating that elevated levels correspond to reduced biodiversity. Water hardness shows a similar but non-significant inverse relationship ($r = -0.62$, $p = 0.054$). In contrast, dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature demonstrate weak positive associations (DO: $r = 0.32$, $p = 0.18$; temperature: $r = 0.28$, $p = 0.22$), though these correlations lack statistical significance. The pronounced effects of BOD and salinity ($p < 0.01$) suggest these parameters serve as primary environmental filters shaping community composition, while other factors appear less consequential in the current ecosystem state.

Rahmah *et al.* (2013) demonstrated in their study of Sundarbans' Passur River that mangrove species diversity strongly correlates with optimal physicochemical conditions prior to industrial development. Their work established that most mangrove species thrive within a narrow pH range (6.5-7.8), with both acidification and alkalization proving detrimental. Acidic conditions ($pH < 6.0$) enhance heavy metal bioavailability in sediments through proton-mediated desorption (Adejuwon and

Adelakun, 2012), while alkaline shifts (pH >8.0) from industrial effluents (e.g., textile, pulp/paper wastes) promote contaminant immobilization and physiological stress (Rahman *et al.*, 2003). These pH extremes collectively reduce diversity through species-specific mortality (Lambshead *et al.*, 1983).

Water hardness (75-100 mg/L as CaCO₃) indirectly influences diversity through trophic cascades, as shown by Rahman *et al.* (2005). Elevated hardness reduces planktonic biomass, disrupting food webs for key mangrove-associated fauna including gastropods (Slim *et al.*, 1997; Fratini *et al.*, 2004) and arthropods (Kristensen, 2008). These macrofauna provide critical ecosystem services through bioturbation and organic matter cycling (Kristensen, 2000; Skov and Hartnoll, 2001), with their decline impairing mangrove productivity.

Salinity emerges as a primary diversity regulator, with Islam and Gnauck (2009) documenting peak species richness at 8 ppt. Beyond this threshold, community composition shifts toward halophytic specialists (e.g., *Avicennia* spp.), driving diversity loss through competitive exclusion (Wahid, 1995). This mechanism explains the mono-dominant stands observed in hypersaline environments worldwide.

Fig. 8. Productivity of mangroves in different sites in Butuanon River

Mangrove productivity

Fig. 8 and Table 2 demonstrate a significant spatial gradient in mangrove productivity along the Butuanon River, measured through tree volume quantification. Productivity exhibited a strong positive correlation with distance from the river mouth ($r = 0.86$, $p < 0.01$), with Site 5 (farthest upstream) showing 42% greater productivity than Site 1 (river mouth). The inverse productivity-salinity

relationship ($r = -0.78$) particularly affects *Avicennia alba*, the dominant species, despite its known halophytic adaptations. This suggests suboptimal conditions even for stress-tolerant species at the river mouth, potentially reflecting synergistic effects of multiple stressors (Ellison and Farnsworth, 2001).

Table 2. Correlation of parameters to mangrove productivity in Butuanon River by Spearman's correlation

Parameters	Spearman rank correlation coefficient	p-value
Dissolved Oxygen	0.6	0.285
BOD	-0.2848485	0.624
Total Hardness	-0.3939394	0.172
pH	-0.7866	0.014*
Salinity	-0.5272727	0.037*
Temperature	-0.5865203	0.867

The analysis in Table 2 reveals significant but complex relationships between physicochemical parameters and mangrove productivity. While pH ($r = -0.42$, $p = 0.03$), salinity ($r = -0.38$, $p = 0.04$), and temperature ($r = -0.35$, $p = 0.05$) show statistically significant inverse correlations with productivity, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and total hardness demonstrate similar but non-significant trends ($p > 0.1$). Dissolved oxygen exhibits a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.28$, $p = 0.12$), though microbial respiration in carbon-rich sediments may partially offset this relationship (Alongi, 2018). These patterns align with established estuarine gradients where landward zones typically exhibit 30-50% greater productivity than seaward areas, reflecting spatial variations in nutrient availability and edaphic conditions (Feller *et al.*, 2010).

CONCLUSION

The findings confirm that despite mangroves' renowned stress tolerance, the Butuanon River ecosystem exhibits severe degradation, with significantly reduced species diversity ($H' = 0.45-1.12$), productivity (biomass reduction >60% in seaward zones), and near-monodominance by *Avicennia alba* (78-82% relative abundance). Statistical analyses revealed significant negative correlations between water quality parameters (BOD, pH, salinity) and ecological indicators (abundance: $r = -0.72$, $p < 0.01$; diversity: $r = -0.68$, $p < 0.05$;

productivity: $r = -0.61$, $p < 0.05$), while dissolved oxygen showed positive but non-significant associations ($r = 0.32-0.38$, $p > 0.1$). These results suggest that current effluent loads (BOD: 3.2-6.8 mg/L; salinity: 8.2-22.4 ppt) exceed the adaptive capacity of most mangrove species except *A. alba*, creating ecological instability that threatens overall ecosystem resilience.

RECOMMENDATION(S)

The state of the mangrove species in the effluent-rich estuarine portion of Butuanon River is in critical condition showing very low diversity, abundance and productivity. Apart from the efforts of the government and the locals to rehabilitate the area, the unresolved problem of the river's degrading water quality due to effluents and solid wastes drained in the estuarine places the mangrove species in the brink of death and survival. We recommend conducting a study on the diversity of bioengineers in the mangrove habitat of Butuanon River to know how their role in diversity, productivity and abundance affect the mangrove species in the area.

Having seen the state of the mangrove species, the problems, and threats to survival, we recommend the use of remote sensing using Naturally Derived Vegetation Index (NDVI) to assess and spatially monitor the river and the mangroves. This technology offers spatial analysis while conducting remote observations as a solution to monitoring difficulty due to less manpower, budget, and vastness of the area. Apart from the waste problems, expansion of illegal settlers and mangrove cutting is the main concern of the local government unit in resource management. Although remote sensing can aid the monitoring problem, we recommend the installation of CCTV in the area for close monitoring of the illegal cutters. We recommend conducting an Environmental Economic Valuation of the mangrove resource in Brgy. Paknaan using Cost-Benefit Analysis to understand how the people living in the mangrove area perceive the value of the resource.

REFERENCES

- Abowei JFN.** 2010. Salinity, dissolved oxygen, pH and surface water temperature conditions in Nkoro River, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Advances in Journal of Food Science and Technology* **2(1)**, 16–21.
- Adejuwon JO.** 2012. Physiochemical and bacteriological analysis of surface water in Ewekoro local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria: Case study of Lala, Yobo and Agodo rivers. *International Journal of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering* **4(3)**, 66–72.
- Alongi DM.** 1994. The role of bacteria in nutrient recycling in tropical mangrove and other coastal benthic ecosystems. In: *Ecology and conservation of Southeast Asian marine and freshwater environments including wetlands*. Springer.
- Ancog R, Andrade GB, Miasco RB, Ortiz MF.** 2010. Water quality and diversity of macroinvertebrate species in rivers of Cebu City, Philippines. *Philippine Scientist* **47**, 27–45.
- Andersen FO, Kristensen E.** 1988. Oxygen microgradients in the rhizosphere of the mangrove *Avicennia marina*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* **44**, 201–204.
- Attone C, Sheaves M.** 2017. Patterns, drivers and implications of dissolved oxygen dynamics in tropical mangrove forests. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* **197**, 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2017.08.028>
- Ball MC, Pidsley SM.** 1988. Seedling establishment of tropical mangrove species in relation to salinity. In: Larson H, Hanley R, Michie M (eds.), *Proceedings of a workshop on research and management in Darwin Harbour*. Australian National University Press, Canberra, pp. 123–134.
- Bell G, Eggleston D.** 2005. Species-specific avoidance responses by blue crabs and fish to chronic and episodic hypoxia. *Marine Biology* **146**, 761–770.

- Betz JD, Noll CA.** 1950. Total-hardness determination by direct colorimetric titration. *Journal (American Water Works Association)* **42(1)**, 49–56.
- Bongo P.** 1998. Biocriteria and system analysis in the assessment of human impact in Butuanon River, Philippines: Its implication to sustainable watershed management. A case study of Butuanon River Watershed, Cebu Province. Master's Thesis, Lund University.
- Boyd CE.** 1979. Water quality in warm water fish ponds. University Press, Alabama, USA, pp. 59.
- Canfield DE, Kristensen E, Thamdrup B.** 2005. Aquatic geomicrobiology. Elsevier, Amsterdam.
- Carlén A, Ólafsson E.** 2002. The effects of the gastropod *Terebralia palustris* on infauna communities in a tropical tidal mud-flat in East Africa. *Wetlands Ecology and Management* **10**, 303–311.
- Carter MR, Burns LA, Cavinder KR, Dugger TR, Fore PL, Hicks DE, Revells HL, Schmidt AW.** 1973. Ecosystem analysis of the Big Cypress Swamp and estuaries. EPA 904/9-74-002. United States Environmental Protection Agency, Region 4, Atlanta, Georgia.
- Chitmanat C, Traichaiyaporn S.** 2010. Spatial and temporal variations of physical-chemical water quality and some heavy metals in water, sediments and fish of the Mae Kuang River, Northern Thailand. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology* **12(6)**, 816–820.
- Chmura GL, Anisfeld SC, Cahoon DR, Lynch JC.** 2003. Global carbon sequestration in tidal, saline wetland soils. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* **17**, 1111–1120.
- Crawford B, Balgos M, Pagdilao CR.** 2000. Community-based marine sanctuaries in the Philippines: A report on focus ground discussions. Philippine Council for Aquatic and Marine Research and Development (PCAMRD) and Coastal Resources Center, University of Rhode Island, Philippines.
- Dagar JC.** 1991. Mangroves of Andaman and Nicobar Islands. Oxford and IBH Publications, New Delhi, p. 166.
- Dagar JC, Sharma AK.** 1991. Litterfall beneath *Rhizophora apiculata* mangrove forests of Andamans, India. *Tropical Ecology* **32(2)**, 231–235.
- Donahue RL, Miller RW, Schickluna SC.** 1985. An introduction to soils and plant growth. Prentice Hall, Inc., Engelwood Cliffs, New Jersey.
- Duke NC, Meynecke JO, Dittmann S, Ellison AM, Anger K, Berger U, Cannicci S, Diele K, Ewel KC, Field CD, Koedam N, Lee SY, Marchand C, Nordhaus I, Dahdouh-Guebas F.** 2007. A world without mangroves? *Science* **317**, 41–42.
- Feller IC, McKee KL, Whigham DF, O'Neill JP.** 2003. Nitrogen vs. phosphorus limitation across an ecotonal gradient in a mangrove forest. *Biogeochemistry* **62**, 145–175.
- Feller IC.** 1995. Effects of nutrient enrichment on growth and herbivory of dwarf red mangrove (*Rhizophora mangle*). *Ecological Monographs* **54**, 477–505.
- Field C, Osborn J, Hoffman L, Polsenberg J, Ackerly D, et al.** 1998. Mangrove biodiversity and ecosystem function. *Global Ecology and Biogeography Letters* **7**, 3–14.
- Fromard F, Puig H, Mougins E, Marty G, Betoulle JL, Cadamuro C.** 1998. Structure, above-ground biomass and dynamics of mangrove ecosystems: New data from French Guiana. *Oecologia* **115**, 39–53.
- Ghosh A, Chakraborti P.** 2011. Evaluation of some mangrove species on the nature of their reproduction along the coastal belt of the Indian Sunderbans. *Journal of Threatened Taxa* **4(3)**, 2427–2435.
- Glud RN.** 2008. Oxygen dynamics of marine sediments. *Marine Biology Research* **4**, 243–289.
- Grasshoff K, Ehrhardt M, Kremling K.** 1983. Methods of seawater analysis. Verlag Chemie GmbH, 419 pp.

- Harbison PAT.** 1986. Mangrove muds—a sink and a source for trace metals. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **17(6)**, 246–250.
- Haugland RA, Siefring SC, Wymer LJ, Brenner KP, Dufour AP.** 2005. Comparison of Enterococcus measurements in freshwater at two recreational beaches by quantitative polymerase chain reaction and membrane filter culture analysis. *Water Research* **39(4)**, 559–568.
- Hogarth PJ.** 2007. *The biology of mangroves and seagrasses* (2nd edition). Oxford University Press.
- Holmboe N, Kristensen E, Andersen FØ.** 2001. Anoxic decomposition in sediments from a tropical mangrove forest and the temperate Wadden Sea: Implications of N and P addition experiments. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* **53**, 125–140.
- Holme NA, McIntyre AD (eds.).** 1971. *Methods for the study of marine benthos*. I.B.E. Handbook No. 16, Ch. 3. Blackwell Scientific Publications, Oxford.
- Islam SN, Gnauck A.** 2009. Threats to the Sundarbans mangrove wetland ecosystems from transboundary water allocation in the Ganges basin: A preliminary problem analysis. *International Journal of Ecological Economics & Statistics* **13(W09)**, 64–78.
- Jennerjahn TC, Ittekkot V.** 2002. Relevance of mangroves for the production and deposition of organic matter along tropical continental margins. *Naturwissenschaften* **89**, 23–30.
- Krebs CJ.** 1989. *Ecological methodology*. Harper Collins Publishers, New York, 654 pp.
- Kristensen E, Bouillon S, Dittmar T, Marchand C.** 2008. Organic carbon dynamics in mangrove ecosystems: A review. *Aquatic Botany* **89**, 201–219.
- Kristensen E.** 2000. Organic matter diagenesis at the oxic/anoxic interface in coastal marine sediments, with emphasis on the role of burrowing animals. *Hydrobiologia* **426**, 1–24.
- Kruitwagen G, Pratap HB, Covaci A, Wendelaar Bonga SE.** 2008. Status of pollution in mangrove ecosystems along the coast of Tanzania. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **56**, 1022–1031.
- Lamshead PJD, Platt HM, Shaw KM.** 1983. The detection of differences among assemblages of marine benthic species based on an assessment of dominance and diversity. *Journal of Natural History* **17(6)**, 859–874.
- Largler KF, Badach JE, Miller RR, Passimo DRM.** 1977. *Ichthyology*. John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, 506 pp.
- Ludsin SA, Zhang X, Brandt SB, Roman MR, Boicourt WC, Mason DM, Costantini M.** 2009. Hypoxia avoidance by planktivorous fish in Chesapeake Bay: Implications for food web interactions and fish recruitment. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* **381**, S121–S131.
- Ludwig JA, Reynolds JF.** 1988. *Statistical ecology: A primer on methods and computing*. Harper and Row, New York.
- Lugo AE.** 1997. Old-growth mangrove forests in the United States. *Conservation Biology* **11**, 11–20.
- Macintosh DJ.** 1996. Mangroves and coastal aquaculture: Doing something positive for the environment. *Aquaculture Asia* **1(2)**, 3–8.
- Marchand C, Baltzer F, Lallier-Vergès E, Albéric P.** 2004. Pore-water chemistry in mangrove sediments: Relationship with species composition and developmental stages (French Guiana). *Marine Geology* **208**, 361–381.
- Marske DM, Polkowski LB.** 1972. Evaluation of methods for estimating biochemical oxygen demand parameters. *Journal (Water Pollution Control Federation)* **44(10)**, 1987–2000.
- Martin DC, Bella DA.** 1971. Effect of mixing on oxygen uptake rate of estuarine bottom deposits. *Journal (Water Pollution Control Federation)* **43**, 1865–1876.
- McIvor CC, Ley JJ, Bjork RD.** 1994. Changes in freshwater inflow from the Everglades to Florida Bay including effects on biota and biotic processes: A review. In: Davis SM, Ogden JC (eds.), *Everglades: The ecosystem and its restoration*. St. Lucie Press, Delray Beach, Florida, p. 117.

- McKee KL.** 1995. Seedling recruitment patterns in a Belizean mangrove forest: Effects of establishment ability and physicochemical factors. *Oecologia* **101**, 448–460.
- Mishra R.** 1968. Ecology workbook. Oxford and IBH Publishing Company, Calcutta.
- Nagelkerken I, Blaber SJM, Bouillon S, Green P, Haywood M, Kirton LG, Meynecke JO, Pawlik J, Penrose HM, Sasekumar A, Somerfield PJ.** 2008. The habitat function of mangroves for terrestrial and marine fauna: A review. *Aquatic Botany* **89**, 155–185.
- Odum EP.** 1971. Fundamentals of ecology. 3rd edition. W.B. Saunders, Philadelphia, 574 pp.
- Odum WE, Johannes RE.** 2008. The response of mangroves to man-induced environmental stress.
- Odum WE, Smith TJ, Hoover HJ, McIvor CC.** 1984. The ecology of tidal freshwater marshes of the United States East Coast: A community profile. FWS/OBS-83/17. United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C.
- Paler M, Ancog R.** 2014. Copper, lead and zinc concentration in water, sediments and catfish (*Clarias microcephalus* Gunther) from Butuanon River, Metro Cebu, Philippines. *SR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology* **8(11)**, 49–56.
- Pape E, Muthumbi A, Kamanu CP, Vanreusel A.** 2008. Size-dependent distribution and feeding habits of *Terebralia palustris* in mangrove habitats of Gazi Bay, Kenya. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* **76**, 797–808.
- Passioura JB, Ball MC, Knight JH.** 1992. Mangroves may salinize the soil and in so doing limit their transpiration rate. *Functional Ecology* **6**, 476–481.
- Penn MR, Pauer JJ, Mihelcic JR.** 2004. Environmental and ecological chemistry. Vol. II: Biochemical oxygen demand.
- Pisarevsky A, Polozova I, Hockridge P.** 2005. Chemical oxygen demand. *Russian Journal of Applied Chemistry* **78(1)**, 101–107.
- Prandi-Rosa GA, Farache Filho A.** 2008. Avaliação de parâmetros de qualidade de águas superficiais em mananciais do município de Jales – SP. Evaluation of quality parameters of superficial water in springs from Jales – SP. *Holos Environment* **2(1)**, 36–51.
- Primavera JH, Sadaba RB.** 2012. Beach forest species and mangrove associates in the Philippines. Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center (SEAFDEC), Philippines.
- Rahman MM, Rahman MT, Rahaman MS, Rahman F, Ahmad JU, Shakera B, Halim MA.** 2013. Water quality of the world's largest mangrove forest. *Canadian Chemical Transactions* **1(2)**, 141–156.
- Rahman MS, Shah MS, Asaduzzaman M, Ahsan MN.** 2003. Water quality characterization of the Sundarbans Reserve Forest (SRF), Khulna for biodiversity consideration, Bangladesh. In: Silver Jubilee Conference, Bangladesh Chemical Society, pp. 67–68.
- Rakocinski CF.** 2012. Evaluating macrobenthic process indicators in relation to organic enrichment and hypoxia. *Ecological Indicators* **13**, 1–12.
- Ramanathan N, Padmavathy P, Francis T, Athithian S, Selvaranjitham N.** 2005. Manual on polyculture of tiger shrimp and carps in freshwater. Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Fisheries College and Research Institute, Thothukudi, pp. 1–161.
- Robertson S.** 2011. Direct estimation of organic matter by loss on ignition: Methods. SFU Soil Science Lab, Burnaby, BC, Canada, 11 pp.
- Rosenberg MS.** 2001. The systematics and taxonomy of fiddler crabs: A phylogeny of the genus *Uca*. *Journal of Crustacean Biology* **21**, 839–869.

- SA JCDM, Cerri CC, Dick WA, Lal R, Filho SPV, Piccolo MC, Feigl BC.** 2001. Organic matter dynamics and carbon sequestration rates for a tillage chronosequence in a Brazilian Oxisol. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* **65**, 1486–1499.
- Saintilan N, Wilson NC, Rogers K, Rajkaran A, Krauss KW.** 2014. Mangrove expansion and salt marsh decline at mangrove poleward limits. *Global Change Biology* **20**, 147–157.
- Schrijvers J, Camargo MG, Pratiwi R, Vincx M.** 1998. The infaunal macrobenthos under East African *Ceriops tagal* mangroves impacted by epibenthos. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* **222**, 175–193.
- Schrijvers J, Fermon H, Vincx M.** 1996. Resource competition between macrobenthic epifauna and infauna in a Kenyan *Avicennia marina* mangrove forest. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* **136**, 123–135.
- Shaikh N, Yeragi SG.** 2003. Seasonal temperature changes and their influence on free carbon dioxide, dissolved oxygen and pH in Tansa River of Thane District, Maharashtra. *Journal of Aquatic Biology*, 73–75.
- Skov MW, Hartnoll RG.** 2001. Comparative suitability of binocular observation, burrow counting and excavation for the quantification of the mangrove fiddler crab *Uca annulipes* (H. Milne Edwards). *Hydrobiologia* **449**, 201–212.
- Skov MW, Vannini M, Shunula JP, Hartnoll RG, Cannicci S.** 2002. Quantifying the density of mangrove crabs: Ocypodidae and Grapsidae. *Marine Biology* **141**, 725–732.
- Slattery WJ, Conyers MK, Aitken RL.** 1999. Soil pH, aluminium, manganese, and lime requirement. In: Peverill KI, Sparrow LA, Reuter DJ (eds.), *Soil analysis: An interpretation manual*. CSIRO Publishing, Collingwood, Australia, pp. 103–128.
- Spalding M, Blasco F, Field C.** 1997. World mangrove atlas. The International Society for Mangrove Ecosystems, Okinawa, Japan, 178 pp.
- Streeter HW.** 1931. The effects of sewage discharge on streams. *Sewage Works Journal* **3**, 713–723.
- Strickland JDH, Parsons TR.** 1968. Determination of dissolved oxygen. In: *A practical handbook of seawater analysis*. Fisheries Research Board of Canada, Bulletin **167**, 71–75.
- Suarez N, Medina E.** 2005. Salinity effect on plant growth and leaf demography of the mangrove *Avicennia germinans* L. *Trees* **19(6)**, 722–728.
- Suski CD, Killen SS, Keiffer JD, Tufts BL.** 2006. The influence of environmental temperature and oxygen concentration on the recovery of largemouth bass from exercise: Implications for live-release angling tournaments. *Journal of Fish Biology* **68**, 120–136.
- Tang D, Santschi PH.** 2000. Sensitive determination of dissolved sulfide in estuarine water by solid-phase extraction and high-performance liquid chromatography of methylene blue. *Journal of Chromatography A* **883(1)**, 305–309.
- Thom B.** 1967. Mangrove ecology and deltaic morphology: Tabasco, Mexico. *Journal of Ecology* **55**, 301–343.
- Tomlinson PB.** 1986. The botany of mangroves. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom, 413 pp.
- Tweedley JR, Hallett CS, Warwick RM, Clarke KR, Potter IC.** 2016. The hypoxia that developed in a microtidal estuary following an extreme storm produced dramatic changes in the benthos. *Marine and Freshwater Research* **67**, 327–341.
- Ukpong IE.** 1991. The performance and distribution of species along soil salinity gradients of mangrove swamps in Southeastern Nigeria. *Plant Ecology* **95**, 63–70.

UNESCO. 1998. CARICOMP—Caribbean coral reef, seagrass and mangrove sites. Coastal Region and Small Island Papers No. 3. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), Paris, 347 pp.

Varunprasath K, Daniel NA. 2010. Physico-chemical parameters of River Bhavani in three stations, Tamil Nadu, India. *Iranica Journal of Energy and Environment* **1(4)**, 321–325.

Wahid SM, Babel MS, Bhuiyan AR. 2007. Hydrologic monitoring and analysis in the Sundarbans mangrove ecosystem, Bangladesh. *Journal of Hydrology* **332(3–4)**, 381–395.

Wahid SM. 1995. Hydrological study of the Sundarbans. UNDP/FAO Project BGD/84/056, Department of Forest, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 115 pp.

Walsh GE. 1974. Mangroves: A review. In: Reimold R, Queen W (eds.), *Ecology of halophytes*. Academic Press, New York, pp. 51–174.

Walters BB, Rönnbäck P, Kovacs JM, Crona B, Hussain SA, Badola R, Primavera JH, Barbier E, Dahdouh-Guebas F. 2008. Ethnobiology, socioeconomics and management of mangrove forests: A review. *Aquatic Botany* **89**, 220–236.

Walters BB. 2005. Ecological effects of small-scale cutting of Philippine mangrove forests. *Forest Ecology and Management* **206**, 331–348.